

Hydroxamic Acid Complexes of Platinum Metals

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Preparation of isomeric tris (oxaldihydroxamato) dirhodium (III) has been described. Ruthenium (III) benzohydroxamato complex, an inner complex salt, has also been described. Benzo-, salicyl and anthranilohydroxamic acids have been found to form complexes with rhodium (III) in which they occupy only four co-ordination positions. Benzohydroxamic acid complex of palladium (II) has been characterised. Metastable oxaldihydroxamic acid complex of palladium (II) has been prepared and its decomposition to crystalline glyoxalhydroxamato complex, at room temperature in the presence of moisture and air, has been noted. Formation of anthranilohydroxamic acid complex of iridium (III); and salicyl- and benzohydroxamic acid nitrosyl complexes of iridium (II) have been studied. Preparation of iridium (II) glyoxal hydroxamic acid complex has also been described.

Complexes of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Ti, V, Mo, Zr, Nb, and Ta with a large number of hydroxamic acids were reported by Chakraburty¹ and recently the preparation of a oxaldihydroxamic acid complex of Rh (III) was reported by the present author.² Preparation of several hydroxamic acid complexes of some platinum metals are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tris (Benzohydroxamato) Ruthenium (III):—An aqueous solution (50 ml.) of benzohydroxamic acid (5 g.) was added to an aqueous solution (50 ml.) of ruthenium (III) chloride (0.25 g.) and the mixture (pH 2-3) was kept at 50-60° for 2-3 hr with vigorous stirring when a dark red brown precipitate separated from the reddish brown solution, which was then filtered off after cooling, washed with hot water and purified by crystallization from alcohol giving dark red crystals which were washed with ether and dried in air. [Found; C, 49.6 ; H, 3.42; N, 8.26; and Ru, 20.20%. Ru (C₇H₆O₂N)₃ requires: C, 49.44; H, 3.52; N, 8.25 and Ru, 19.94%] M.p., 98°. The compound is sparingly soluble in water but dissolves in sodium hydroxide giving a yellow solution. It is highly soluble in alcohol, benzene, toluene etc, giving non conducting solutions.

Tris (Oxaldihydroxamato) Dirhodium (III):—The concentrated hydrochloric acid solution of previously prepared³ rhodium (III) oxaldihydroxamato complex was gradually and carefully neutralised with solid sodium acetate, the sodium chloride

1 A. K. Chakraburty, "The Structure of Metallic Complexes of Hydroxamic acids and their uses in Analytical Chemistry"—paper presented to the Symposium on the Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds, Agra, 7-8 Feb., 1959.

2 R. S. Mishra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 400.

solid formed being repeatedly dissolved by water, which on diluting and cooling gave red violet precipitate which was filtered, washed repeatedly with hot water, alcohol and ether and dried in air. [Found: Rh, 37.15; C, 13.2; H, 1.15 ; and N, 14.9%.]

$\text{Rh}_2 \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{COH} : \text{NO} \\ \text{COH} : \text{NO} \end{array} \right]_3$ requires: Rh, 36.78; C, 12.85; H, 1.07 and N, 15%.]

The compound is insoluble in water and sodium hydroxide but soluble in methanol, ethanol and mineral acids.

Sodium Dichlorobis Benzohydroxamato) Rhodate (III) Pentahydrate:—To an aqueous solution (50 ml.) of rhodium (III) chloride (1 g.), buffered to 5-6 pH by aqueous sodium acetate solution, was added aqueous solution (60 ml.) of benzo-hydroxamic acid (3 g.), acidified with dilute acetic acid, and the mixture was heated for 40-50 minutes and for further 1 hr with a few drops of acetic acid when sufficient light chocolate precipitate appeared. It was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried in air. [Found: Rh, 18.4; Na, 4.1; C, 30.81; H, 3.94; N, 4.88 and Cl, 15%. Na [Rh (C₇H₆O₂N)₂ Cl₂]. 5H₂O requires : Rh, 18.43 ; Na, 4.11 ; C, 30.6. H, 3.94; N, 5 and Cl, 15.14%.]

Water is completely lost at 126° and the compound is fairly stable up to 320° without melting.

The compound is insoluble in water, benzene, ether, acetone and ethylacetate but is sparingly soluble in methanol, and in hot water, when freshly prepared, giving light red brown solution.

Sodium Dichlorobis (Salic hydroxamato) Rhodate (III):—To an aqueous solution (100 ml.) of rhodium (III) chloride (1 g.) acidified with acetic acid, was added equal volume of concentrated aqueous solution of salicylhydroxamic acid and the mixture was buffered to pH 4-5 by concentrated aqueous sodium acetate solution and it was heated strongly for 7-8 hr when light brown precipitate appeared. It was cooled, filtered, washed with hot water, ethanol, and benzene and dried in air. [Found: Rh, 20.75; Na, 4.7; C, 33.14; H, 2.55; N, 5.35 and Cl, 14%. Na [Rh (C₇H₆O₃N)₂ Cl₂] requires, Rh, 20.56; Na, 4.59; C, 33.33; H, 2.39; N, 5.59 and Cl, 14.17%]. M.p., 286° (decomposes). The compound is almost insoluble in water but soluble in mineral acids and highly soluble in methanol and ethanol.

Sodium Dichlorobis (Anthranilohydroxamato) Rhodate (III) Trihydrate:—An aqueous solution (100 ml.) of rhodium (III) chloride (1 g.) was treated with clear aqueous solution (100 ml.) of sodium salt (5 g.) of anthranilohydroxamic acid rendered acidic by dilute hydrochloric acid and the mixture after addition of a few mls of ethanol, was heated strongly till slight turbidity appeared. Now the mixture was refluxed for 3-4 hr and allowed to cool when sufficient pale yellowish red precipitate settled which was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried in air. [Found: Rh, 19; Na, 4.25; C, 30.65; H, 3.75; N, 10 and Cl, 12.65% Na [Rh (C₇H₇O₂N₂)₂ Cl₂]. 3H₂O requires; Rh, 18.62; Na, 4.15; C, 30.38; H, 3.61;

N, 10.12 and Cl, 12.83%]. M.p. 308° (partial). All the water molecules are lost at 128° when the colour changes to brown black.

The compound is insoluble in water, soluble in mineral acids as well as in methanol and ethanol but with difficulty in amyl alcohol.

Bis (Oxalhydroxamic acid hydroxamato) Palladium (II):—To a well cooled saturated aqueous solution (200 ml.) of oxaldihydroxamic acid was added carefully an aqueous solution (100 ml.) of palladium (II) chloride (1 g.) in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide gas, which on stirring for 40-50 min. gave dull buff coloured precipitate which was filtered quickly, washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried over sulphuric acid charged in carbon dioxide gas. [Found: Pd, 31.28;

C, 14.23; H, 1.60 and N, 15.93%. Pd $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{CO.NHO} \\ 1 \\ \text{CO.NHOH} \end{array} \right)_2$ requires: Pd, 30.95; C, 13.92; H, 1.74; and N, 16.24%].

The compound is insoluble in water and alcohol but sparingly soluble in acetic acid and soluble in mineral acids and sodium hydroxide.

The compound decomposes in air when moist but in the presence of silica or carbon dioxide gas or ether vapour, it is fairly stable even moist.

Bis (Glyoxalhydroxamato) Palladium (II) Trihydrate:—The aqueous pasty mass of bis (oxalhydroxamicacidhydroxamato) palladium (II) (5 g.) was heated at 50-60° for 6-8 hr when violet brown crystals were produced. With the aid of ethanol, the product was filtered, washed repeatedly with hot ethanol, then ether and dried in air.

[Found: Pd, 32.03; C, 14.6; H, 2.82 and N, 7.98%. Pd $\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \text{CHO} \\ 1 \\ \text{CONHO} \end{array} \right\}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires: Pd, 31.68; C, 14.28; H, 2.97 and N, 8.31%].

The compound is sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in methanol, ethanol, carbon tetrachloride, and acetone, sparingly soluble in ether but soluble in mineral acids, and also in sodium hydroxide yielding greenish violet solution. Water is completely lost at 102° and the compound decomposes on further strong heating with the evolution of a brown gas.

Bis (Benzohydroxamato) Palladium (II) Monohydrate:—To an aqueous solution (60 ml.) of palladium (II) chloride (2 g.), buffered carefully to 5-6 pH by concentrated aqueous sodium acetate solution, was added aqueous solution (60 ml.) of benzohydroxamic acid (6 g.) and after thoroughly stirring the mixture, the pale yellowish green precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and benzene respectively and dried in air. [Found: Pd, 27.2; C, 42.12; H, 3.28 and N, 7.83%. Pd $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires: Pd, 26.89, C, 42.35; H, 3.52, N, 7.57%].

Water is lost at 110° completely. The compound is insoluble in water, benzene, acetone and chloroform, sparingly in alcohols (greenish yellow solution) and ether, and soluble in sodium hydroxide giving light greenish yellow colouration.

Bis (Glyoxal Hydroxamato) Iridium (II) Trihydrate:—To an aqueous solution (100 ml.) of sodium hexachloroiridate (IV) (2 g.) was added equal volume of well cooled, concentrated aqueous solution of oxaldihydroxamic acid. The mixture was strongly heated for 6½-7 hr with continuous vigorous stirring when slight turbidity appeared. Now it was allowed to cool gradually and the greenish brown violet crystals formed were filtered, washed with hot water, alcohol and ether and dried in air. [Found: Ir, 46.2; C, 11.68; H, 2.23 and N, 6.17%]. Ir (C₂H₂O₃N)₂. 3H₂O requires; Ir 45.67; C, 11.34; H, 2.36 and N, 6.61%]

The compound is insoluble in water, alcohols and ether but soluble in mineral acids. It loses water completely at 108°.

Sodium Monochlorobis (Benzohydroxamato) Nitrosyliridate (II):—An aqueous solution (100 ml.) of sodium hexachloroiridate (IV) (2 g.) was treated with aqueous solution (100 ml.) of benzohydroxamic acid (6 g.) and the mixture was heated slowly for 1 hr and strongly for further 2½-3 hr when brown black precipitate appeared which, after cooling, was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and benzene and dried in air. [Found: Ir 34.42; Na, 4.35; C, 31, H, 2.42; N, 7.87 and Cl, 6.12% Na [Ir (C₇H₆O₂N₂)₂ (NO) Cl] requires: Ir, 34.86; Na, 4.15, C, 30.35; H, 2.16; N, 7.58 and Cl, 6.41%]. M.p., 300° (decomposes). The compound is almost insoluble in water, highly soluble in alcohol, and sparingly soluble in ether.

Sodium Monochlorobis (Salicylhydroxamato) Nitrosyliridate (II):—To an aqueous solution (100 ml.) of sodium hexachloroiridate (IV) (2 g.) was added concentrated aqueous solution (100 ml.) of salicyl hydroxamic acid and the mixture was gently heated and the blue black precipitate formed was then filtered after cooling, washed with hot water, ethanol and benzene and dried in air. [Found: Ir, 33.4; Na, 4.1; C, 29.43; N, 7.2; H, 2.31 and Cl, 5.79%. Na [Ir (C₇H₆O₃N)₂ (NO) Cl] requires: Ir, 32.96; Na, 3.92; C, 28.69; N, 7.17; H, 2.04 and Cl, 6.06%.] The compound is insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in alcohol but highly soluble in ether giving fine indigo blue solution. It gives blue fluorescence in dilute nitric acid solution.

Sodium Dichlorobis (Anthranilohydroxamato) Iridate (III):—The sodium hexachloroiridate (IV) solution (as in the previous preparation) was refluxed with half its volume of concentrated aqueous alcoholic solution of sodium salt of anthranilohydroxamic acid rendered acidic by dilute acetic acid for 2-2½ hr when on cooling violet brownish precipitate separated from the dark brown solution, which was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried in air. [Found: Ir, 33.21; Na, 4; C, 29.22; H, 2.6; N, 9.73; and Cl, 11.89%, Na [Ir (C₇H₇O₂N₂)₂ Cl₂] requires: Ir, 32.76; Na, 3.9; C, 28.52; H, 2.37; N, 9.5 and Cl, 12.05%]

The compound is insoluble in water and ether, is soluble in methanol, ethanol and mineral acids but with difficulty in amyl alcohol.

Further work on the aforesaid complexes and a few hydroxamic acid complexes of platinum is in progress.

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